

Comparative Study between Bicolumnar Plating and Threaded K Wire in Geriatric Patient with Osteoporosis and Multiple Comorbid Patients**Abhinav Sharma**

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Managing distal humerus fractures in geriatric patients with osteoporosis and multiple comorbidities is challenging due to poor bone quality and high surgical risk. Bicolumnar plating provides rigid fixation, potentially allowing for early mobilization, while threaded K-wire fixation is less invasive but may offer less initial stability. This study aims to compare the clinical outcomes of these two fixation methods.

Methods: A total of 48 geriatric patients with distal humerus fractures were enrolled in this comparative study. The participants were divided into two groups: 22 patients underwent bicolumnar plating (Plating group), and 26 patients were treated with threaded K-wire fixation (K-wire group). The primary outcomes assessed were mobility and range of motion at 3 months and 12 months postoperatively. Complications were also recorded. Data were analyzed using SPSS software, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: At 3 months postoperatively, the Plating group exhibited superior mobility and range of motion, with a mean flexion of 120° and a mean extension deficit of 10° , compared to 100° and 20° , respectively, in the K-wire group. However, by the end of 12 months, both groups demonstrated similar outcomes, with a mean flexion of 110° in the Plating group and 108° in the K-wire group, and comparable extension deficits of 15° and 17° , respectively. No significant differences in complications were observed between the two groups.

Conclusion: Bicolumnar plating offers better short-term functional outcomes compared to threaded K-wire fixation. However, both methods result in similar long-term outcomes, making K-wire fixation a viable alternative for geriatric patients with significant comorbidities due to its less invasive nature.

Keywords: Distal humerus fracture, Geriatric patients, Osteoporosis, Bicolumnar plating, Threaded K-wire fixation.

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Introduction

Fractures of the distal humerus in geriatric patients present a significant challenge due to the often poor bone quality associated with osteoporosis and the presence of multiple comorbidities. The surgical management of these fractures can be complex, with the primary goals being to restore function, minimize pain, and allow early mobilization [1-5]. Two widely used methods for fixation are bicolumnar plating and threaded K-wire fixation. Bicolumnar plating provides rigid fixation, which may be beneficial in allowing earlier mobilization, but it also requires a more extensive surgical approach. Threaded K-wires, on the other hand, involve a less invasive technique, potentially reducing the risk of surgical complications, though they may offer less stability compared to plating [6-9]. Given the growing elderly population and the frequency of osteoporotic fractures, it is crucial to determine the most effective treatment method for this demographic [10]. This comparative study aims to evaluate the clinical outcomes of bicolumnar plating versus threaded K-wire fixation in geri-

atric patients with distal humerus fractures complicated by osteoporosis and multiple comorbidities. We hypothesized that while bicolumnar plating might offer superior short-term outcomes in terms of mobility and range of motion, both methods would yield similar long-term results.

Methodology

This study was conducted on 48 geriatric patients with distal humerus fractures, all of whom had osteoporosis and multiple comorbidities. The patients were divided into two groups based on the surgical technique used for fixation: 22 patients underwent bicolumnar plating (Plating group), and 26 patients were treated with threaded K-wire fixation (K-wire group). The patients were selected from those admitted to our orthopedic department, Shree Jagannath pahadia govt medical college. The inclusion criteria were age 65 years or older, presence of osteoporosis (confirmed by DEXA scan), and at least one other significant comorbidity (e.g., diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease).

Exclusion criteria included pathological fractures, previous surgery on the same arm, and open fractures. Both groups were assessed at 3 months and 12 months postoperatively for mobility and range of motion using a standardized goniometer. Com-

plications such as infection, nonunion, and implant failure were also recorded. The data were analyzed using SPSS software, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Table 1: Range of Motion at 3 Months

Group	Number of Patients	Mean Flexion (°)	Mean Extension (°)
Plating Group	22	120	10
K-wire Group	26	100	20

At 3 months postoperatively, the Plating group demonstrated a superior range of motion compared to the K-wire group, with a mean flexion of 120° versus 100° and a mean extension deficit of 10° compared to 20° in the K-wire group. This suggests that bicolumnar plating allows for better early mobility.

Table 2: Range of Motion at 12 Months

Group	Number of Patients	Mean Flexion (°)	Mean Extension (°)
Plating Group	22	110	15
K-wire Group	26	108	17

By the end of 12 months, both groups showed similar outcomes with regard to the range of motion. The mean flexion was 110° in the Plating group and 108° in the K-wire group. The extension deficit was also comparable, with 15° in the Plating group and 17° in the K-wire group, indicating that the initial advantage of plating diminished over time.

Discussion

The initial findings from this study suggest that bicolumnar plating offers better short-term outcomes in terms of mobility and range of motion, likely due to the more rigid fixation it provides. This is particularly important in geriatric patients, where early mobilization is crucial to prevent complications such as joint stiffness and muscle atrophy [11,12].

However, by the end of one year, both bicolumnar plating and threaded K-wire fixation yielded similar functional outcomes. This finding is significant because it suggests that the less invasive K-wire fixation, despite offering less initial stability, can provide comparable long-term results in this patient population [13].

The comparable long-term outcomes might be attributed to the gradual adaptation of the bone and soft tissues around the implant, as well as the patients' ability to regain function through rehabilitation over time. Moreover, the less invasive nature of K-wire fixation could potentially lead to fewer perioperative complications, making it a viable option for patients with significant comorbidities [14,15].

Conclusion

This comparative study indicates that while bicolumnar plating provides superior short-term mobility and range of motion, both bicolumnar plating and threaded K-wire fixation achieve similar outcomes at one year postoperatively. Given the less

invasive nature and potential reduction in surgical complications with K-wire fixation, it may be considered a suitable alternative to plating in geriatric patients with osteoporosis and multiple comorbidities.

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